

Determination of Trace Metals in Fish, Water, and Sediments of Some Ponds in Ado, Ikere and Iyin Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

¹D. F. Adewumi ²I. A. Daniyan, ³K. A. Adigun and ⁴A. O. Adeodu

¹Department of Chemistry, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

^{2,4} Department of Mechanical & Mechatronics Engineering, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

³ Department of Statistics, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: D. F. Adewumi, E-mail: wumiadetj@yahoo.com

Received: June 13, 2015, Accepted: July 18, 2015, Published: July 18, 2015.

ABSTRACT

Many trace elements are essential to human being but in some cases there is only a small safety range requirement to avoid toxicity. In this study, traces of some minerals in samples of water, fish, and ponds sediments at Ado, Ikere and Iyin Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria were determined. Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer was used for the determination of Cadmium, Copper, Cobalt, Iron and Manganese. Complexometric titration was used to determine Magnesium and Sodium while Calcium and Potassium were determined by flame photometer. Results of these determinations show that Cadmium was not detected at all in all the water and sediment samples of the three ponds, it was not detected in Ado and Ikere water and sediment samples. Cobalt was detected in both water and sediment samples from Iyin and Ado Ekiti fish ponds. It was observed that even though Phosphorus and Magnesium were not detected in all the water samples, the concentration ranges from $0.87 \pm .09$ to 41.67 for Phosphorus and 72.94 to 867.13 mg/L for magnesium in both fish and sediment samples. Generally, it was observed that the concentration of these metals ranges from 2116.67 ± 62.36 for Calcium to $0.004 \pm .001$ for Copper. The concentration trends of these minerals shows highest concentration in fish, followed by sediment and least in water thus confirming the presence of trace metals in the selected fish, water and pond sediments.

Keywords: Atomic Absorption Spectrometer, Concentration, Flame Photometer, Trace Elements,

INTRODUCTION

Trace elements form a group of generally poorly understood substances that normally occur in concentrations that are less than 1mg dm^{-3} in water. Many trace elements are essential to human being but in some cases there is only a small safety range requirement to avoid toxicity. Although some metals has been known for centuries as industrial poisons, the coming of industrial age led to more wide spread occurrence of occupational disease related to exposure to variety for toxic metals. It is essential to monitor the level of water pollution not only for health reasons but also for industrial and agricultural purposes. Human activities to a large extent have continued to deny people access to improved water supply. Heavy metals are known as metallic elements with high molecular weight or specific gravity which produces toxicity by forming complexes or ligands with organic compounds and active site enzymes. Metals are introduced into water bodies through oil spillage, sewage effluents, auto emission, industrial activities such as mining, canning, electroplating, rock weathering etc.[7]. Metals after entering water bodies may be precipitated, suspended in water or may be taken up by fauna and flora and eventually accumulate in marine organisms consumed by human beings [6]. At high concentration, they are dangerous because they bio accumulate faster in living things such as fish than they are broken down (Nelson and Parker, 1983). These metals are present in human and animal waste and can enter environment if wastes are released without treatment. The challenge however is the application of suitable technology for the control of organic micro-pollutants and heavy metals.

Various categories of pollutants are known to pollute water environment but those of heavy metals are non biodegradable hence accumulate in the body system causing serious health challenges. It is well known that mineral element are necessary for life as some of them like Fe, Zn, Cu etc. are essential nutrients required small amounts for enzymatic biochemical activities [2, 5]. Some other minerals such as Cd, Hg are potential poisons not even required in small amount but have valuable industrial applications with resultant effect on the environment if not controlled [6, 9]. Virtually all metals are toxic if the exposure level is sufficiently high to exceed the tolerance level [4]. Industrial waste may contaminate environment or endanger public health if discharged directly into water bodies resulting in increase in temperature of the water, thereby causing death of aquatic life. Some heavy metals may accumulate in marine organism resulting in food poisoning. About 80% of all diseases and more than one third of all deaths in developing countries are caused by contaminated water [10]. It has been confirmed that with adequate supplies of safe drinking water, the incidence of some illness and death could drop by as much as 75% [3]. The presence of heavy metals in soil is as a result of hazardous waste, spent catalyst or coke dust, tank bottom and sludge treatment processes [11] Cited by [1]. The intense consumption of refined petroleum products in Nigeria has put pressure on petroleum depots and companies thus becoming major sources of air, water and soil pollution[11].

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The research is a case study of selected fish ponds in Ado, Ikere and Iyin Ekiti, Ekiti State (Nigeria). The various samples (water, fish and soil) used for the analysis of trace metals were collected from the fish ponds. Water sample was collected at various locations along the pond, using a clean plastic container rinsed with deionized water. The fresh fish samples collected from the pond were *Tilapia zili* and *Claria gariepinus*. The fish samples were collected at the upstream and downstream of the pond using locally made wire net of 2.5 mm diameter. Soil samples were collected from different points with the use of soil sampler.

Water Samples Preparation

About 5 cm³ of concentrated HNO₃ was added to 250 cm³ of water samples in 500 cm³ beaker. The solution was evaporated to near dryness on hot plate. After cooling, another concentrated nitric acid was added with the beaker covered with water glass. Gentle heating continued until digestion was completed. The concentration was filtered and transferred to 50 cm³ standard flask and diluted to mark with distilled water.

Fish Samples Preparation

The whole fish was dried in an electric oven at 70-80°C for three days. The fish samples were pulverized using clean mortar and pestle to produce it powdered form. A homogenized 2 g of the ground fish was weighed in analytical balance and ashed in a furnace at 550°C. The samples were put in flask and 10 ml each of concentrated HNO₃ and HCl were added. The samples were digested for 2-3 hours, filtered into 100 cm³ standard volumetric flask and made to mark with distilled water.

Soil Sediment Samples Preparation

Air dried soil samples were sieved using 200 mm mesh. 5g of the soil was weighed into 100 ml conical flask and was digested with 10 ml of concentrated HNO₃ and 2 ml HCl and the content was filtered into 100 ml standard flask and made to mark with distilled water.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 : Concentration of metals (PPM) in sample from Iyin Ekiti

Sample s	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cd	Cu	Co	Na	K	P	Mg
Water	9.4± 1.14	ND	0.22 ±.16	ND	0.004 ±.001	ND	3.73±.17	1.73±.21	ND	ND
Sediment	31.40 ±10.25	6.4 ±1.4	2.23 ±1.4	ND	0.03 ±.01	ND	54.67±.29	23.33 ±6.34	0.93±.47	105.35 ±41.32
Fish	1616.67 ±61.82	21.0 ±8.1	2.63 ±.16	0.06 ±.01	0.30 ±.10	0.35 ±.08	190.60 ±14.14	146.67 ±4.71	41.67 ±1.70	737.46 ±99.99

ND = NOT DETECTED.

Table 1.2 : Concentration of metals (PPM) in sample from Ado Ekiti.

Sample s	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cd	Cu	Co	Na	K	P	Mg
Water	1.37±.78	0.06 ±1.03	0.08 ±.04	ND	ND	ND	1.27±.41	0.09 ±.29	ND	ND
Sediment	28.87 ±1.47	2.06 ±.09	0.14 ±.04	ND	ND	ND	43.33 ±1.89	28.0 ±1.41	0.87 ±.09	72.94 ±19.2
Fish	1630.0 ±160.62	19.20 ±2.67	4.60 ±.86	0.04 ±.01	5.87 ±3.37	0.31 ±.07	276.67 ±20.55	185.0 ±10.80	40.67 ±.47	842.82 ±69.72

Trace Metal Detection

The digested samples water, soil and fish were analysed for heavy metals such as: Fe, Mn, Cd, Cu and Co by Bulk 210 model Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. Standards were prepared using salts of the metals. The instrument was switched on and the relevant hollow cathode lamp as well as wave length fixed for each metals. Air-acetylene flame was employed. The standard for each metal were then sprayed into flame as well as the samples and the corresponding absorbance values were taken. Both standards and samples were read under the same conditions. Potassium and sodium contents of samples were determined using flame photometer.

Hardness

To 100 ml of the aliquot sample was added 2 ml of NH₄/NH₄Cl buffer to bring the pH value to 9.0. About 0.2 g of Erichrome black T indicator was added which formed a wine red colour. The whole content was stirred and titrated against 0.01 M EDTA to blue end point.

Hardness:

$$\frac{0.01 \text{ M of EDTA} \times \text{Titration value} \times \text{molar mass of CaCO}_3 \times 1000}{\text{Ml of sample}} \quad (1)$$

Presence of Phosphate

4 ml of prepared ascorbic acid were pipetted and 1.06 g of ascorbic acid was weighed and made up to 200 ml. The sample was added to make the required volume 50 ml. The solution was thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand for 30 minutes. A cloudy colour was observed. The absorbance was then determined at 420 nm using corning colorimeter 253. Readings of unknown were read from the standard curve and the result was calculated as follow:

$$\text{Mg /LPO}_4^{3-} = \frac{\text{Reading from curve} \times 1000 \times D}{\text{Ml of sample}} \quad (2)$$

Table 1.3 : Concentration of metals (PPM) in sample from Ikere Ekiti..

Sampl es	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cd	Cu	Co	Na	K	P	Mg
Water	8.81±3.60	0.16 ±0.01	0.80 ±.43	ND	ND	0.04±.0 01	2.60±0.28	1.53±0.04	ND	ND
Sedim ent	10.17±4.67	5.87 ±3.06	0.44 ±0.32	ND	ND	0.21 ±0.05	67.67 ±3.30	15.67 ±2.25	1.27 ±0.19	97.25 ±19.85
Fish	2116.67 ±62.32	20.1 ±0.63	3.60 ±2.60	0.03 ±0.004	0.27 ±0.02	0.35 ±0.06	283.33 ±28.67	196.67 ±20.93	40.67 ±0.47	867.13 ±19.65

Table 1.4: Acceptable limit for heavy metals (mg /kg)

Fe	Mn	Cd	Cu	Mg	P	Ca
0.30	0.10	0.05	0.05	500	0.40	500

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Calcium and Magnesium

The calcium and magnesium concentrations in the fish samples were extremely high as compared to the rest of the samples. This is so because calcium is needed towards the bone formation of the fish and that calcium and magnesium are major soil constituents. The calcium concentration in sample ranges from 1.37±.78 ppm in Ado Ekiti water sample to 2116.67±62.32 in Ikere Ekiti fish samples, while magnesium was not detected in the water samples but its concentration ranges from 72.94±19.25ppm in Ado Ekiti sediment to 867.12±19.65ppm in Iyin fish sample. The variation in concentration of these metals might be due to the fact that the magnesium is too reactive to occur naturally but found its way as a constituent of mineral deposit such as dolomite and magnesium carbonate.

Sodium, Potassium and Phosphorus.

The concentration of these metals took similar trends within the samples with phosphorus not detected in all the water samples. The sodium concentration was found to be within the range of 1.27 ± .41mgdm⁻³ in Ado Ekiti water sample to 283.30±28.67mgdm⁻³ in Ikere Ekiti fish sample. Potassium result ranges from 0.09±.29 to 196.67±20.93mgdm⁻³ for Ado Ekiti water sample and Ikere fish sample respectively. In line with this, Phosphorus was found to be within the range of 0.87±0.9mgdm⁻³ for Ado Ekiti sediments to 41.67±1.70 in Iyin Ekiti fish sample.

Cadmium, Cobalt and Copper.

Results show that these metals were determined in traces as expected. Cadmium and Cobalt were not detected in water and sediment samples of both Iyin and Ado Ekiti locations. However, their concentrations ranges from 0.04mgdm⁻³ of Copper in Iyin Ekiti water sample to 5.87mgdm⁻³ of Copper in Ado Ekiti fish sample. The presence of copper in these samples may be traced to the geological structure of these ponds and also the leaching effects during raining season or weathering. Again some fish ponds are being used for domestic purposes where there is no adequate security. Among these human activities are washing of clothes, taking of baths and washing of plates. All these activities can incorporate these toxic metals in the aquatic system.

Iron and Manganese

The Iron trend shows the highest concentration of 21.0 ± 8.1mgdm⁻³ for Iyin Ekiti fish sample to the least concentration of 0.06mgdm⁻³ in Ado Ekiti water sample, although it was not detected in Iyin Ekiti water sample. The manganese

concentration ranges from 0.8±0.04 to 4.6mgdm⁻³ in Ado Ekiti water and fish samples respectively.

CONCLUSION

In view of overall results, it is observed that fish has the highest concentration of these metals with calcium having the highest concentration and copper the least. The major concern is that the presence of these toxic metals Cadmium, Copper and Cobalt should be checked so that the threshold limit may not be exceeded all of a sudden.

REFERENCES

1. Adeodu, A. O., I. A. Daniyan and A. S. Yusuff (2013). Assessment of Soil, Water and Plant Pollution by Heavy Metals from Petroleum and Petrochemical Companies in Nigeria. *Int. Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*.4(7) 2401- 2412.
2. Buss, D. and J. Robertson (1976). *Manual of Nutrition*. Her Majesty's Stationers Officers Publisher, London. 8th Edition, pp. 32-40.
3. Charles, E., Kupchella, and C. Marganet (1999). Environmental Science. *Bio resource Journal* 29(2) 244-305.
4. Dowdeswell, E. (1996). "Editorial Comments on Water". *Our Planet*, 8 (3):1
5. Fostner, U. and Withman, G. T. U. (1979). *Metal Pollution in the Aquatic Environment*. SpringerVerlag, Berlin. pp. 99-118
6. Laws, E. A. (1977). *Aquatic Pollution*. John Wiley and Sons, Newyork. pp. 301-369.
7. Marr, I. L. and M. S. Creaser (1983). *Environmental Chemical Analysis*. Blackie and Sons Publisher Ltd, 1st Edition, pp. 104.
8. Nelson, M. and P. Parker (1983). *Advanced Level Physics*. 5th Edition. Heinemann Educational Book, London.

9. Owolabi, R. A. (1992). Determination of Metals in Fish and Associated Water and Soil Samples From Selected Ponds in Ondo and Edo State, Nigeria. M. Tech. Thesis, Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.
10. Olajuyigbe, A. E. and J. O. Fasakin (2010). Some Factors Impacting on Access to Improved Sources of Domestic Water Supply in a Rapidly Urbanizing State Capital in South-Western Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Technology*.1(1) 42-51
11. World Health Organization (1993). Guidelines for Drinking Quality Water, W H O, Geneva.

Citation: D. F. Adewumi et al.. (2015) Determination of Trace Metals in Fish, Water, and Sediments of Some Ponds in Ado, Ikere and Iyin Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. *J. of Physical and Chemical Sciences*.V3I2. DOI: 10.15297/JPCS.V3I2.05

Copyright: © 2015 D. F. Adewumi. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.